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Comparative dating of charcoal, tooth and ceramic samples from the Polutepe archaeological site in Azerbaijan

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The radiocarbon dating method was used to date the age of a charcoal sample from the Polutepe archaeological site in the Jalilabad district of Azerbaijan. Polutepe is the largest Neolithic-Eneolithic monument in the Caucasus. A charcoal sample excavated at the Polutepe site was dated by the conventional radiocarbon method at 4270 ± 160 BC, which agrees with the stratigraphic estimated dates. ESR method has also been applied to determine the age of tooth enamel found in Polutepe archaeological site. The investigated object was presumably the lower jaw of a cow with well-preserved tooth. The mean age of the sample was determined as 5420 ± 130 BC years. The age of fragments of the ancient pottery sample from the same archaeological site has been estimated by employing Thermoluminescence dating method. The age of the sample was calculated by an additive dose method as 4360 ± 530 BC years which are in line with the charcoal samples.